

D11.3: Networking activities I

D11.3: Networking activities I / WP 11, T11.3

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DISTENDER

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

DISTENDER is a project funded under Horizon Europe's Cluster 5: Climate, Energy, and Mobility, specifically aimed at better understanding of the interactions between climate change impacts and risks, mitigation and adaptation options. Given the multifaceted nature of climate change, the project adopts a multi-disciplinary approach that combines both mitigation (actions that reduce the progress of climate change) and adaptation (actions that adapt life to a changing climate) strategies.

Interdisciplinary collaboration is key in work related to climate change adaptation and mitigation. To engage with experts in the field, DISTENDER will actively seek out and collaborate with fellow EU projects and different networks. This engagement allows exchange and the sharing of knowledge during the implementation of the project. Strong engagements will enable the generation of medium-term outcomes and long-term impact. This approach will help establish relationships with relevant organizations and individuals and foster knowledge sharing with important stakeholders.

Networks are a crucial tool in accelerating the process of raising awareness about the project, promoting acceptance of the approaches employed, and encouraging the uptake of the solutions developed. Forming relations with other players in the field of climate change thus benefits the project implementation by giving outside perspectives. Beyond the lifetime of the project, networks can provide opportunities in resource, expertise, or funding for the further development of outcomes. Engaging with relevant networks at varying levels will enable DISTENDER to establish lasting relationships with key stakeholders.

1.2 Purpose and scope

The sustainability of the results produced in DISTENDER relies on the degree of awareness, acceptance, and uptake of the results in society. To facilitate this process, networking activities play an important role in creating and nurturing relations with key stakeholders in the field of climate change.

The objective of the network engagement plan is to:

1. Provide a strategy to broaden the network in which DISTENDER is embedded in detailing the specific networks and other EU projects working in the area of climate change where engagement will be beneficial, and
2. Outline the range of activities planned to contact and engage with aforementioned networks during the lifetime of the project.

The scope of networks identified corresponds to those with local, regional, and national reach in terms of the consortium members and case studies, as well as international and EU-wide networks and projects. Projects identified are those resulting from the topic Socio-economic risks of climate change in Europe, Cluster 3 on Disaster Resilient Societies and H2020, if ongoing.

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This network engagement plan is strongly related to the deliverables within WP11 Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. Awareness-raising activities and materials enable the successful engagement of networks for the dissemination of information. Successful network engagement will then further build upon successful exploitation of project results.

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2 Methodology

2.1 Defining engagement objectives within DISTENDER

Networking activities are an essential part of the nine objectives of the DISTENDER project. Objective 9 is specifically connected with work package 11 and calls for a “network to promote and exchange the outputs of the projects with other EU and international initiatives about climate change.” It specifies several elements of the networking activities, being

- to **broaden the networks and their engagement**
- with actions to **identify, contact and establish lasting relationships** over time
- at **local, regional, national and international levels**,
- as to identify **collaboration opportunities, new agreements and collaborative research**
- with specific interest in the **sister projects of this call**, cluster 4 and cluster 6.
- Collaboration among **Working Groups I, II, and III of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change** will be facilitated and enhanced.

These elements have been taken up in this networks engagement plan and are addressed in the upcoming chapters.

Complementarily, an online survey was sent out to the DISTENDER partners to capture their expectations and envisioned contributions to the networking activities. Following the thought pattern of the Golden Circle by Simon Sinek¹, partners were asked to formulate in their own words:

- the ultimate *goal* or expectations from networking activities, meaning the “WHY?” behind task 11.3,
- *how* they could contribute to the networking goal and whether, linking to “HOW?” they could interact with networks and EU projects as part of their role in DISTENDER, and
- *what* activities they already had in mind that contribute to the overall networking goal, so the “WHAT?”.

2.2 Identifying, analysing, and prioritizing relevant networks and EU projects

The networks engagement plan addresses two target groups that are of interest for the DISTENDER networking activities: thematically related networks and EU-projects. The roadmap for developing the engagement strategy consists of several steps and is visualized in figure 1.

¹ Sinek, S. (2009), Start with Why: How Great Leaders Inspire Everyone to Take Action, London: Penguin Group

Figure 1: Roadmap for the development of engagement strategy for networks

As a first step, existing networks as well as thematically relevant EU projects have been **identified** based on i) the information provided in the Grant Agreement, ii) an initial query to the project partners as part of the preparation of D11.1 Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, and iii) a CORDIS search conducted by S2i. Both Grant Agreement and D11.1 contain a comprehensive list of target audiences for dissemination activities, including professional and research networks, and outline the scope of potentially relevant EU-projects for DISTENDER networking.

The impact section of the Grant Agreement outlines a range of professional and research networks to be engaged within WP11. As of professional networks, it suggests the following: Climate Chain Coalition, ETIP-SNET, ETP ZEP, Global Bioenergy Partnership, Coalition for Energy Savings Plastics Europe, Bioenergy Europe, Spring Cluster, Assobioplastiche, EI – Energy Institute, BBIA - Biobased and Biodegradable Industries Association, BBI-JU, BRENET- building and Renewable Energies Network of Technology, CEEweb Biodiversity, and JCSS – Joint Committee on Structural Safety. Additionally, the following research networks are suggested: Institute for Climate Research and Environmental Control, ISEE - The International Society for Ecological Economics, Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, EIEE – European Institute on Economics and the Environment, EARTO, Association of European Operational Research Societies, Plastics Europe, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, Knowledge-Action Network - KAN- on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events, and Resilience Alliance.

In the query, which was conducted in October 2022 in the context of D11.1, project partners had been asked to name the platforms/networks/initiatives in which their organization was an active member in (table 1). Also, partners had been asked to name other European or local platforms/networks/initiatives to which they saw cooperation potential and synergies for DISTENDER (table 2). The information collected served as a starting point for the inventorying of relevant networks while during the online survey sent to partners for the preparation of D11.3, partners were asked to add any missing networks to this list.

Table 1: Platforms / Networks / Initiatives where DISTENDER partners are an active member in

MEMBERSHIP			
Platforms / Networks / Initiatives which your organisation is active member in			
Key Platform / Network / Association / Initiative name	Link (if available)	Geographical scope: International / European / National (please specify country)	Partner who included the input
METREX	https://www.eurometrex.org/	European metropolitan cities network	CMT0
National urban planning institute	https://www.inu.it/	National	CMT0
UERA - Urban Europe Research Alliance	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/uera/	Europe	UB
CORAL	https://twitter.com/coraleurope?lang=es	Europe	KVC
EIP on AHA Reference Site Collaborative Network	http://tscn.eu/	Europe	KVC
Covenant on Demographic Change	https://www.agefriendlyeurope.org/	Europe	KVC
CLM-Community (Climate Limited-area Modelling-Community)	https://clmcom.scrollhelp.site/clm-community/	Europe	GUF
Med-CORDEX	https://www.medcordex.eu	Europe + Mediterranean	GUF
Bio-based industries consortium (BIC)	https://biconsortium.eu/about	Europe	S2i
Enterprise Europe Network (EEN)	https://een.ec.europa.eu/	Europe	S2i
Smart Cities Marketplace	https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/	Europe	S2i
Clean Energy for EU Islands	https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/	Europe	S2i
Districts of Creativity Network	https://districtsofcreativity.org/	International	S2i
Vanguard Initiative	https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/	Europe	S2i
Network Nature	https://networknature.eu/	Europe	S2i
BBJ-JU	https://www.bbi-europe.eu/	Europe	S2i
Cátedra de transición energética urbana UPV (University chair on urban energy transition)	https://catenerg.webs.upv.es/	Europe	VCE
Mesa de Transición Energética de València (Valencia Energy Transition Table)		Local (Valencia)	VCE
citES 2030	https://diadepues.org/cities-2030/	National (Spain)	VCE
València 2030 Climate Mission (VCE is part of the Coordination Team)	https://www.missionsvalencia.eu/missions/?lang=en	Local (Valencia)	VCE
EIT Climate-KIC	https://www.climate-kic.org/	Europe	UPM
Integrated Mission Group for Security (IMG-S)	https://www.imgs-eu.org/	Europe	ITTI
Public Safety Communications Europe (PSC)	http://www.psc-europe.eu/	Europe	ITTI
Polish Chamber of High Technology	https://iztech.pl/	Local (Poland)	ITTI
European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE)	https://www.eaere.org/	Europe	UNI GRAZ

Table 2: Platforms / Networks / Initiatives to which DISTENDER partners see cooperation potential

SYNERGIES			
Synergies with other European and local Platforms / Networks / Initiatives, that the project should cooperate with (not mentioned already in the previous sheets)			
Key Platform / Network / Association / Initiative name	Link (if available)	Geographical scope: International / European / National (please specify country)	Partner who suggested the synergy
Urban Lab	https://urbanlaborino.it	Local/National	CMT0
Europe Direct Torino		Local/National/Europe	CMT0
METROPOLIS - EMA European Metropolitan Areas Forum	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/newsroom/events/2019/06/ema-european-metropolitan-authorities-forum-european-inclusive-metropolitan-areas-facing-together-social-challenges	Europe	CMT0
Eurocities	https://eurocities.eu	Europe	CMT0
Euromontana	https://www.euromontana.org/en/	Europe	CMT0
Order of Architects, Planners, Landscape Architects and Conservators of the province of Turin	https://www.oato.it/	Piedmont Region	CMT0
Energy Cities	https://energy-cities.eu/	Europe	VCE
Climate ADAPT	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/	Europe	VCE
RED ESPAÑOLA DE CIUDADES POR EL CLIMA	https://redciudadesclima.es	National	Alcorcon
PACTO DE LAS ALCALDÍAS POR LA ENERGÍA Y EL CLIMA	https://www.pactodelosalcaldes.eu	Europe	Alcorcon

With respect to EU projects, a search on CORDIS was conducted by S2i to identify the concrete projects funded within the same call as DISTENDER: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01 - Better understanding of the interactions between climate change impacts and risks, mitigation and adaptation options. Specifically, the sister projects KNOWING and NEVERMORE being funded within the same call topic as DISTENDER, were outlined. The same search was conducted for EU-funded projects within cluster 3 addressing disaster resilient societies. Additionally, CORDIS was screened for ongoing² H2020 projects within the application domains of 'climate change and environment' and 'energy' by addressing 'climatic changes' as the field of science, and within the application domain 'climate change and environment' and the additional keyword search on 'socio-economic' 'risks' 'of' 'climate' 'change'.

² 'Ongoing' as of April 2023

The list of collected EU projects was initially shared with the WP11 lead and the coordinator. In the General Assembly on March 23, 2023, the task 11.3 was introduced to the consortium as well as the need for partners' involvement in the prioritization of networks and EU projects to be preferably engaged. Following this announcement, an online survey was sent to the DISTENDER partners which dealt with the **analysis** of the collaboration potential identified in the GA, D11.1, and the CORDIS search. Partners were asked to review the list of platforms/professional networks/associations/initiatives as well as research networks that were identified by WP11 with respect to their perceived relevance for DISTENDER networking. This also included the networks in which partners were an active member in and to which they saw cooperation potential and synergies. The latter were both rated by the partner proposing them according to a) the networks' interest to engage in DISTENDER networking activities and b) the relevance/ importance of involving the respective network. The professional and research networks taken from the GA were rated by all partners with respect to their interest be involved in DISTENDER networking activities.

At this point, the inventory of suggested networks has been quite comprehensive. In order to decide how to focus available resources and engage them throughout DISTENDER, the **prioritization** of networks to be engaged was done in a similar manner than for the stakeholder identification in WP2. The suitability of the stakeholder engagement matrix for DISTENDER has been described in D2.1. The matrix used (figure 2) positions the networks according to their interest to engage in DISTENDER networking activities and the relevance of involving them. Based on this matrix, the networks are classified according to the four positions in the matrix: keep into account, keep informed, meet their needs, and manage closely. Based on the classification of the networks in the four positions, also referred to as the levels of engagement, different engagement approaches and activities are presented in chapter 5.

Figure 2: Stakeholder engagement matrix, following approach of Robert Newcombe³

³ Newcombe, R. (2003). From client to project stakeholders: a stakeholder mapping approach. *Construction Management and Economics*, 21(8), 841–848. doi:10.1080/0144619032000072137

The categorization according to the stakeholder engagement matrix was specifically done for the identified networks as the selected EU projects are understood to be both of high interest and of high relevance, meaning to be managed closely. To be able to further narrow down the most relevant networks and projects for different thematically oriented networking activities, all networks and projects from the engagement level "manage closely" were analysed with respect to their thematic foci on the ten sectors for which DISTENDER aims to provide solutions to adapt and mitigate climate change, being agriculture, biodiversity, energy, finance, forestry, health, quality of life, transport, urban/city, and water (figure 3).

Based on the methodological approach set by the stakeholder matrix for the networks and the thematic classification of the projects, suitable networking activities, a tentative timeline and monitoring structures will be presented in chapter 5.

Figure 3: Sectors addressed in DISTENDER as displayed on the project website⁴

⁴ <https://distender.eu/>

3 Specific networking objectives

As introduced in chapter 2.1, DISTENDER partners were consulted on their expectations and initial ideas on networking activities. Their thoughts on *why* engaging with networks and EU projects will be beneficial for the project, *how* their own contribution could look like, and *what* activities could contribute to the overall goal of networking activities were gathered in an online survey. The answers on the *why* will be addressed in the following while the feedback received on the *how* and *what* will be taken up in chapter 5.

Partners have described the ultimate *goal* of networking activities in DISTENDER in their own words. From the received answers, different categories of objectives can be derived, which can be grouped as bidirectional (1) and unidirectional (2) communication.

(1) Identify synergies, collaboration potential, and exchange knowledge

- To enhance **collaboration and information sharing** to provide insights from different fields of interest,
- To **seek collaborations and synergies** with other projects whose goal is mitigation and adaptation to climate change, both at a local, regional or European Union level
- Identify synergies and **build relationships** that can help to improve the project
- to interact with other case studies in order to **exchange** experiences and ways of implementing mitigation and adaptation measures
- Dissemination of the project in order to **find possible synergies and collaborations** (in the implementation)
- To **know the *state of the art*** of other projects at European level, **get ideas** and **learn about good practices** developed in other project activities
- To **increase individual *knowledge*** with ideas coming from different fields,
- to expand existing knowledge to **review what has been done** in a certain area and **what we can use or update in our work**.
- To **exchange knowledge** with other projects of the same type
- To some extent, we want to **delineate research in DISTENDER from research in other projects**, so we have to know, what other projects are working on, **how results can complement each other** and to use synergies. This also helps **preventing work from being done multiple times**, i.e., if there's data developed for example, we can rely on it rather than doing it again.

(2) Outreach, quality assurance and further utilization of project results

- to **raise *awareness and visibility* of the project** both in professional circles and beyond
- to **spread out the DISTENDER objectives** and results at project level
- **to promote the knowledge** about DISTENDER in other development projects of the same type.
- To **make the decision support system (DSS) and tools developed widely available** to potential users
- **Dissemination of the project *results and methodology***: To disseminate contents from the DSS and their usability for policy makers and other stakeholders (not only from the case studies) to help them with the implementation of adaptation and mitigation strategies.

- Also, the methodology from DISTENDER could be taken as a reference for other scientific projects etc.
- To **determine how adoptable and useful are the DSS system and tools** developed by DISTENDER
- To **obtain feedback** from a wide number of potential users in order to **improve outcomes of the project**

These main objectives of collaboration on one side and outreach and feedback on the other side are also reflected in DISTENDER's overall definition of outcomes and impacts: First, the objectives of DISTENDER networking activities are linked to D10.1 Technical KPI's Definition Framework which formulates outcomes and impacts of the whole DISTENDER project. As such, "network" constitutes one of nine impact dimensions to be monitored and evaluated throughout the project and directs at lasting structural elements resulting from the DISTENDER project⁵.

Second, among the extensive list of DISTENDER outcomes presented in D10.1, the engagement of networks and EU projects contributes to the following ones:

- O.64 Engagement of third-party researchers: Extent to which third parties are reached through other EU research projects and networks which they belong to,
- O.20 Potential DSS networks: No. and extent of (potential) networks formed around the DSS,
- O.21 DSS scientific networks: Extent to which researchers regard the DSS as having the potential for long-term interdisciplinary cooperation,
- O.22 Continuity of networks: Willingness of network members to keep up structures after project end, and
- O.17 Successful outreach: Extent to which Communication, dissemination, and exploitation KPIs are achieved.

O.64 will be indirectly connected to engagement activities with networks and EU projects as the engagement of an organizational entity aims at reaching the individual members of such, for instance third-party researchers. Starting point for measuring O.64 can thus be to take a closer look at the composition of engaged organizations.

O.20 will be of interest to monitor the achievement of the 30 associations and networks to be engaged by focusing on the formation of (new) networks around the DSS. It will be assessed by WP8, WP10 and WP11 towards the end of the project. O.21 targets the perceived potential of the DSS as an anchor for continued interdisciplinary scientific exchange, which touches upon a possible foundation for long-term engagement activities. O.22 addresses the longevity of established and engaged networks beyond the project scope with particular focus on a behavioural aspect, the willingness of its members. Altogether, the outcomes O.20/O.21/O.22 contribute to the impact I.10 Climate Change Action Structures. It comprehends the establishment of fora, platforms, or roundtables for the promotion of climate change action that last beyond the project end. Therefore, the responses of the case studies, follower case studies, researchers, and network members to the mentioned outcomes will influence the qualitative success of the engagement objectives in the long-term perspective.

⁵ D10.1 Technical KPIs Definition Framework, p.28

The successful outreach of the project (O.17) is benchmarked against WP11-specific KPIs as listed in the GA:

- Networking with associations: at least 30 associations & networks reached and engaged
- Participation in external events: at least 2 key events attended by the project at EU/global level
- Organization of project events in cooperation with other EU funded projects to foster replication: min. 3
- One final event (more than 80 participants)
- replication & dissemination webinars to present the DISTENDER solution: >2, min. 30 attendees each, recordings on website accessed by tens of online users.

The networking activities within DISTENDER are oriented on these KPIs and will take up the partners ideas as collected in the survey. *How to engage with networks and what concrete activities could be implemented*, will be presented in chapter 5, complemented by a tentative schedule covering the whole project period.

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4 Relevant networks and EU projects

4.1 Network inventory

As described in chapter 2.2, relevant networks were rated by the partners according to their interest to participate in DISTENDER networking activities and their importance in involving them accordingly. Thereby, the selected EU projects are understood to be both of high interest and of high relevance. Following the approach of the stakeholder engagement matrix, the engagement levels for each network were derived (table 3). Activities linked to the different engagement levels will be presented in chapter 5.

Table 3: Inventory of partner networks with collaboration potential

Network	Level	Interest	Importance / Influence	Engagement level
Relevant EU projects ⁶	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
EI – Energy Institute	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Climate Chain Coalition	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
BRENET- building and Renewable Energies Network of Technology	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
CEEweb Biodiversity	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Global Bioenergy Partnership	Global	Interested	Important	Manage closely
ISEE – The international society for ecological economics	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
EIEE – European Institute for Economics and the Environment	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Knowledge Action Network “KAN” on emergent risks and extreme events	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Resilience Alliance	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely

⁶ Comprises all EU projects as identified in chapter 2.2. The projects will be further categorized in chapter 4.2.

CORAL	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
Smart Cities Marketplace	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
NetworkNature	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
EIT Climate-KIC	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
METROPOLIS - EMA European Metropolitan Authorities Forum	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE)	Europe	Interested	Important	Manage closely
METREX - European metropolitan cities network	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
València 2030 Climate Mission (VCE is part of the Coordination Team)	Local (Valencia)	Not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Eurocities	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Euromontana	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Cluster Spring	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Bioenergy Europe	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
BBIA - Biobased and Biodegradable Industries Association	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
ETIP-SNET	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
ETP ZEP	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Association of European Operational Research Societies	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs

EARTO	Europe	Rather not interested	Important	Meet their needs
UERA - Urban Europe Research Alliance	Europe	Interested	Less important	Keep informed
RED ESPAÑOLA DE CIUDADES POR EL CLIMA	National	Interested	Less important	Keep informed
PACTO DE LAS ALCALDÍAS POR LA ENERGÍA Y EL CLIMA	Europe	Very interested	Less important	Keep informed
EIP on AHA Reference Site Collaborative Network	Europe	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Covenant on Demographic Change	Europe	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Clean Energy for EU Islands	Europe	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Districts of Creativity Network	International	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Vanguard Initiative	Europe	Rather not interested	Not important	Keep into account
Cátedra de transición energética urbana UPV (University chair on urban energy transition)	Europe	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Mesa de Transición Energética de València (Valencia Energy Transition Table)	Local (Valencia)	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account
citiES 2030	National (Spain)	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Urban Lab Torino	Local/National	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Europe Direct Torino	Local/National/Europe	Rather not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Order of Architects, Planners, Landscape Architects and Conservators of the province of Turin	Piedmont Region	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Energy Cities	Europe	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account
Climate ADAPT	Europe	Not interested	Less important	Keep into account

National urban planning institute	National (Italy)	Not interested	Not important	No engagement
Bio-based industries consortium (BIC)	Europe	Not interested	Not important	No engagement
Enterprise Europe Network (EEN)	Europe	Not interested	Not important	No engagement
BBI-JU	Europe	Not interested	Not important	No engagement
CLM-Community (Climate Limited-area Modelling-Community)	Europe	Tbd ⁷	Tbd	Tbd
Med-CORDEX	Europe + Mediterranean	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
Integrated Mission Group for Security (IMG-S)	Europe	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
Public Safety Communications Europe (PSCE)	Europe	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
Polish Chamber of High Technology	Local (Poland)	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
EUROCORDEX ⁸	Europe	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability ⁹	Europe / Global	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
European Climate Foundation (ECF) ¹⁰	Europe	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd
International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT) ¹¹	Europe / Global	Tbd	Tbd	Tbd

Based on this network inventory, additionally to the 45 EU projects, there are 16 networks to be managed closely. Further, there are 13 networks whose needs should be met, three networks to keep informed, and 13 networks to keep into account. As the number of EU projects and networks to be managed closely is very large, an additional differentiation is necessary and will be described in the following (4.2).

⁷ The respective network has not yet been rated by the partners with respect to its interest and relevance for DISTENDER networking activities.

⁸ Suggested by partners during online survey.

⁹ Suggested by partners during online survey.

¹⁰ Suggested by partners during online survey.

¹¹ Suggested by partners during online survey.

4.2 EU project inventory

In the following, an inventory of thematically relevant EU projects for DISTENDER networking activities is established. It consists of projects funded within the same call as DISTENDER, cluster 3 on disaster resilient societies, the call topic HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-01-02-two-stage, and ongoing H2020 projects. The projects are classified according to the ten DISTENDER sectors, being agriculture, biodiversity, energy, finance, forestry, health, quality of life, transport, urban/city, and water (tables 5-7).

The same classification was done for the networks to be closely managed (table 4). This was done to facilitate the future selection of projects and networks for thematically oriented networking activities. The classification shows that most thematic intersections with DISTENDER exist with respect to the focus quality of life (28), biodiversity (25), and finance (23). Overall, many projects link to energy (18), urban/ city (18), water (17), agriculture (17), health (13), forestry (13), but only few to transport (7). It must however be noted that the thematic classification is not exhaustive and that additional linkages with the DISTENDER sectors may be identified as the project continues.

4.2.1 Projects within the same call as DISTENDER

Along with DISTENDER, there are 22 projects funded under call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01: Climate sciences and responses for the transformation towards climate neutrality. Due to their content proximity and their starting dates ranging from June 2022 to January 2023, they are of primary interest for the networking activities. When looking at the sectoral focal areas, many of the projects target biodiversity, energy, finance, quality of life, and water (table 5). It should however be noted that the grouping has been done based on the information available of the respective project websites and on CORDIS, so it may be incomplete. Additional sectoral keywords were added in the table to specify the target of the projects. The grouping has been done to provide a starting point for thematic collaborative activities. More information on the calls within this call topic can be found in Appendix 1.

Among the 22 projects, the highest priority lies on the two sister projects KNOWING and NEVERMORE which are funded within the same call topic as DISTENDER. The connection with representatives of these projects has already been established and the formation of structures for regular exchange is ongoing. A first joint workshop among the three projects will take place at the Sustainable Places conference in June 2023.

4.2.2 Cluster 3 on Disaster Resilient Societies

Within cluster 3 of the work programme 2021/22, there are eight funded projects thematically linking to 'disaster resilient societies' (Appendix 2). The analysis shows that they have started between October and November 2022 and can offer interesting entry points for networking in the areas of climate adaptation, quality of life, and health (table 6). This non-exclusive thematic clustering however only serves as a starting point and can be enlarged once more information is available on the projects. More information on the listed calls can be found in Appendix 2.

4.2.3 HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-01-02-two-stage: Socio-economic risks of climate change in Europe

The call topic has been closed on 27 September 2022 and evaluation results were expected to be communicated in December 2022. As of to date¹², there is no information yet publicly available on the selected projects. The projects to be funded under this call topic will however be monitored in the upcoming months and approached for collaborative networking activities throughout the duration of DISTENDER.

4.2.4 H2020 projects

Based on the selection criteria described in chapter 2.2, 15 ongoing H2020 projects were identified that show thematic linkages to DISTENDER. With respect to the sectoral focus, they address agriculture, biodiversity, energy, finance, quality of life, and urban (table 7). The projects will end between 2023 and 2025 as shown in Appendix 3.

¹² 19.04.2023

Table 4: Thematic analysis of networks to be closely managed with respect to DISTENDER sectors

Networks Sectors	Agriculture	Biodiversity	Energy	Finance	Forestry	Health	Quality of Life	Transport	Urban/ City	Water	Other
EI – Energy Institute			x					x			
Climate Chain Coalition											Digital innovation
BRENET- building and Renewable Energies Network of Technology			x						x		
CEEweb Biodiversity	x	x			x	x				x	policies
Global Bioenergy Partnership	x		x					x			
ISEE – The international society for ecological economics	x	x		x	x					x	Research, education, policy
Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici	x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	research
EIEE – European Institute for Economics and the Environment				x		x	x		x		Digitalization, migration
Knowledge Action Network “KAN” on									x	x	Critical infrastructure

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emergent risks and extreme events												
Resilience Alliance												Research, social-ecological systems
CORAL						x				x		Regional policies
Smart Cities Marketplace			x	x			x	x		x		
NetworkNature	x	x		x	x		x			x		
EIT Climate-KIC	x	x		x	x					x	x	Innovation
METROPOLIS	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	Tools, policies
European Association of Environmental and Resource Economics (EAERE)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	research

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Table 5: Thematic analysis of EU projects funded within the same call as DISTENDER with respect to DISTENDER sectors

EU projects Sectors	Agriculture	Biodiversity	Energy	Finance	Forestry	Health	Quality of Life	Transport	Urban/ City	Water	Other
FOCI						x	x			x	Air quality; policy
GreenFeedBack		x								x	Marine
RESCUE		x									
CircoMod			x				x				Circular economy
CO2NSTRUCT	x	x	x								Circular economy
CircEUlar			x					x	x		Circular economy
MAGICA				x							Knowledge transfer from science to policy
MAIA											Connecting climate change research; exploitation support
ELEVATE							x				Policy
IAM COMPACT				x			x				Policy; non-high income countries
NEVERMORE	x	x	x	x	x		x			x	Adaptation & mitigation; sustainable tourism
KNOWING	x	x	x	x		x	x		x	x	Adaptation & mitigation
Climateurope2				x					x		Climate services, Adaptation & mitigation

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DECIPHER	x											
PATTERN	x			x								Policy
CAPABLE	x										Policy	
ALFAwetlands	x			x	x						x	Land-use change
WET HORIZONS	x										x	Mitigation; restoration
RESTORE4Cs	x										x	Coastal area; adaptation & mitigation
PathFinder	x											
ForestPaths	x		x	x	x							Mitigation & Adaptation
ForestNavigator	x											Mitigation; policy

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Table 6: Thematic analysis of EU projects funded within Cluster 3 on Disaster Resilient Societies with respect to DISTENDER sectors

EU projects Sectors	Agriculture	Biodiversity	Energy	Finance	Forestry	Health	Quality of Life	Transport	Urban/ City	Water	Other
C2IMPRESS							x				Adaptation
DIRECTED							x				Adaptation
The HuT	x				x		x			x	Adaptation
MEDiate				x		x	x				
PARATUS						x		x			Humanitarian relief; adaptation
PEERS											Standardization processes; policy
MOBILISE						x	x				Pandemics
ONELAB						x					Pandemics

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Table 7: Thematic analysis of ongoing H2020 projects with respect to DISTENDER sectors

	Agriculture	Biodiversity	Energy	Finance	Forestry	Health	Quality of Life	Transport	Urban/ City	Water	Other
EMB3Rs			X								Mitigation
DRYvER		X					X			X	Mitigation & adaptation
BiodivScen		X									
MIND STEP	X	X									Policies
BiodivClim		X									Adaptation & mitigation
RECEIPT	X			X			X				
CASCADES	X			X			X				Adaptation;
NAVIGATE				X			X				Mitigation & adaptation; policy
ENGAGE				X			X				Mitigation; policy
CityxChange			X				X		X		
POCITYF			X				X		X		
eLTER PLUS	X	X					X		X	X	
FOOD TRAILS	X						X		X		
NEGEM			X								mitigation
RESPOSE			X						X		

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5 Networks engagement strategy and plan

5.1 Engagement approaches

Chapter 4.1 has formulated the different levels of engagement for the networks, based on their score (high or low) on interest and relevance/influence. The engagement approaches corresponding to these engagement levels are visualized in Figure 4 with respect to the effort to be invested and number of networks to be possibly engaged.

Figure 4: Engagement approach pyramid¹³

Starting from the bottom of the pyramid to the top: Pull communication is one-directional, from sender to recipient. Thereby, information is made available by the sender while the recipient can decide whether to engage with it, for instance by clicking on a website. It is suitable for networks of rather low influence/relevance to the overall DISTENDER project and of low interest to actively engage with the project. A concrete example of pull communication would be information or further links displayed on the DISTENDER website. This engagement approach involves the least effort for the sender and allows to address a large number of networks.

Push communication is as well one-directional. The sender however actively broadcasts information to the networks to be engaged using various channels such as newsletters, policy briefs, or flyers. In this case, the sender already needs to know the recipients/ its target group a bit to produce information, that is relevant to them. Push communication can

¹³ Stakeholdermap.com

be used for networks of low influence/relevance and low to high interest in engaging with the project.

Consultation requires an action from the recipient, meaning to typically respond to the question that is asked by the sender. The influence of the recipient is limited to the consultation situation while having no responsibility for the further use of the consultation results. Consultation can happen in different settings, for instance when the network has little influence/relevance to the overall project development but is highly interested in it, or the opposite, when having a high influence/relevance to the overall project and little interest in engaging actively. In both cases, collecting the voice of the respective network will be beneficial as it is either easy-to-engage or has a position that needs to be considered in the project.

Participation means that sender and recipient are part of the same team, however with varied responsibilities. The recipient is engaged in concrete activities of the team, works towards similar goals, and has a certain influence on the project developments. For DISTENDER networking activities this can mean that a network or EU project is involved in a joint webinar.

Lastly, among the different engagement approaches, a partnership represents the greatest effort to sender and recipient. It includes joint learning, activities, and decision-making and represents a shared responsibility for results. Sender and recipient can be interchanged and interact on an equal level. Within DISTENDER networking, this type of engagement could for instance comprise a joint application with the sister projects KNOWING and NEVERMORE for the dissemination services of the Horizon Results Booster towards the end of the project.

To sum up, and as figure 4 shows, more effort is needed to closely manage a network via organizing a joint webinar for instance. Consequently, the number of networks to be closely managed is smaller than the ones that can be kept informed, for instance via social media postings. The current network inventory in 4.1 names six networks to be managed closely additionally to the 45 EU projects and four networks whose needs should be met. Networking activities to engage with these networks will be presented in 5.2. The mentioned networks to keep informed and to keep into account will be addressed via targeted communication and dissemination activities within WP11.

5.2 Networking activities and monitoring

The suggested activities to engage networks and EU projects are closely linked to the suggestions made by the project partners as part of the conducted survey. Within the survey, partners have described *how* they could contribute to achieving the goals (of networks engagement) based on their role in DISTENDER and *what* activities could be performed. From the received answers, different categories of implementation means are derived:

1. Participation and organization of collaborative events
 - **Participating in events, and workshops** on specific topics, and bringing my competencies. Participating in **calls for papers** and other editorial opportunities.

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- Networking between different institutions and **presentation of previous work** and exchange of experiences with each other.
 - On the other hand, we can **make use of our networks** and/or contact other ones via e-mail, on-line calls etc. in order to establish the connection. Maybe **attending specific networking events** (eg. clustering etc) from the EU could be useful to find contacts from another EU projects, also via specific meetings/**conferences**.
 - Facilitating contact with potential members of the network
 - I will **create new meeting and participate in Conferences** where several EU projects are represented. Sustainable Places 2023 in Madrid is a clear example.
 - **To participate at open project workshops/webinars** of other relevant projects, communicate with researchers of other projects
 - Participating in **European Civil Dialogue groups**; participating in future **conferences, seminars**, etc.
2. Mentioning DISTENDER in day-to-day business
- As a follower case study our role is limited. We can **mention the project while interacting with other networks and projects**.
 - Our daily work in a town hall of a medium size city does not require participation in research projects of the same type as DISTENDER, therefore I cannot contribute on how to collaborate with other similar projects. Despite the above, Alcorcón is part of several associations at the European and national level that work for climate change, and once Distender has finished its work, the **dissemination of its results through these associations could be improved**.
 - To inform partners of another project where we are involved about DISTENDER
3. Involvement of case studies' local network
- We suggest **contacting the partners from the CSs** to get information about their local/regional/national networks.
4. Transparent communication of learnings
- Through an accurate description of the CMTO case study, **highlighting the critical issues and strengths that will emerge** from project activities,
 - Disseminating DISTENDER activities and outcomes through **newsletter and other information materials** (brochures, etc).

Further, partners have suggested concrete first ideas on how to establish lasting relationships with networks and EU project:

- Propose the **development of specific activities together with the networks and EU-projects** which might be relevant for all.
- By participating together in **calls for papers** on specific topics.
- Continuous interactions/communication with institutions all the time, not just during the project DISTENDER.
- Have lasting relationships is possible but **performing effective added activities is difficult** due to in this last case, **we do not have an EU funding project involved** and this will be part of future proposals.
- Engaging and collaborating with them; **providing services and useful information** derived from DISTENDER

- A **study visit** could be a good starting point, a **new project** could also improve relationship.

The answers of partners highlight that the engagement activity must lie within the interest of the partners' organizations and that existing funding is bound to the project duration of DISTENDER. Nevertheless, physical meetings, sharing of relevant information and collaboration in additional projects can be favorable to strengthen the cooperation.

Building on the received partner input, different types of activities will be organized for, and with the networks and EU projects to be managed closely and whose needs are to be met, including public and semi-public webinars, direct consultations, and face-to-face meetings at conferences. The thematic planning of the events may be oriented towards the ten DISTENDER sectors but also tailored to the needs of the involved project partners, networks and fellow EU projects. A tentative timeline including the different activities is presented in chapter 5.3.

Public webinars are part of the regular dissemination and communication measures aim to reach relevant people in professional and research networks by sharing learnings on how to bridge the gap between adaptation and mitigation measures. This is a unidirectional dissemination measure aiming at the communication of project developments and (expected) project results. The DISTENDER project website and its social media channels will be used to announce public networking events. The public webinars will not be exclusively targeted at networks and EU projects to be managed closely and whose needs are to be met. Additionally, all networks identified as either important/relevant or interested will be invited.

Semi-public webinars or joint workshops are clustering events with inventoried EU projects and networks aiming to learn from each other and to share knowledge regarding climate change adaptation and mitigation linked to the DISTENDER sectors. Thereby, the knowledge exchange is focal, meaning that the communication is bidirectional. The expected duration of such webinars will range between 1-2 hours each, in exceptional cases, such as a physical workshop with a large number of participants, it may take longer. The clustering events will be organized throughout the project and in close collaboration with the WP11 lead, aiming at two semi-public clustering events per year.

To strengthen the commitment of the involved networks and EU projects, they will be asked to sign a letter of intent (LoI), expressing their willingness to actively cooperate with DISTENDER. To also ensure equal conditions for constructive knowledge exchange among the participants, the LoI can include specifications on how the generated knowledge can be used by the individual project consortia to appropriately protect intellectual property. By the end of the project, it is intended to have 30 signed LoIs, including EU projects and networks.

Direct consultation will be used to engage with the IPCC representatives. As outlined in the GA, DISTENDER results will be regularly presented to them to i) inform their work within the IPCC and ii) to receive feedback from them on the project implementation. Project advances and results are transferred to them annually. The subsequent consultations will be a mean to discuss on methods and approaches used or planned to be used within DISTENDER. It will further serve to receive the representatives' feedback on which information will be most useful for policymakers, thereby allowing to set priorities

accordingly. The results generated within DISTENDER shall ultimately serve as input for upcoming IPCC reports, and in the meantime provide visibility to the project.

Participation to **conferences** is an important mean to contact relevant networks and EU project representatives, but also to deepen the collaboration with existing ones. Thereby, **face-to-face meetings** with previously identified individuals allow to promote the project itself, to exchange knowledge and promote their participation in planned DISTENDER webinars. The participation of project partners to conferences at local, regional, national or international level will be monitored by WP11.

Ultimately, the **stabilisation of networking efforts** will be simulated by building on face-to-face meetings and joint clustering events. Close networks and EU projects, such as the DISTENDER sister projects, but also those with whom the cooperation will have been constructive and mutually beneficial, will be approached and opportunities for further collaboration, new agreements and collaborative research evaluated. Based on mutual demands, the foundation for a network that outlasts the project duration, formalized by a memorandum of understanding and a regular mean of exchange, is envisioned.

As also indicated by a partner in the conducted survey, the involvement of the case studies local network is key to not only collaborate at European level but also at national and regional scale. Case studies' already existing and currently expanding network is very valuable to increase the outreach of the project developments via interactive activities. Therefore, we will maintain the exchange with WP2 and WP9 to align the networking efforts to the substantive work in the case studies. This will involve the exchange on planned events in the case studies and the invitation of their network to project wide dissemination activities.

5.3 Tentative timeline of networking activities

Table 8 takes up the different activities to be conducted within Task 11.3 and distributes them across the project period. It can be noted that until May 2023, the coordinator already participated in four international conferences and thereby represented the DISTENDER project, being the International Conference on Environment and Climate Change (ICECC), International Conference on Future Environment and Energy, the Global Energy Meeting, and the Going Green – CARE INNOVATION.

Two more conferences at EU/ global level, Sustainable Places and Urban Future, are already planned for June 2023. At Sustainable Places, a joint workshop with DISTENDER's two sister projects KNOWING and NEVERMORE is foreseen, thus laying the foundation for their collaboration. Besides further joint webinars and/ or workshops on project relevant topics, another opportunity to strengthen the connection with DISTENDER's sister projects, may be the joint application to the dissemination services of the Horizon Results Booster in 2024. This would allow to strengthen the dissemination efforts of the individual projects via a joint identity with respect to the climate change mitigation and adaptation measures developed in the three projects. A possible joint application of the three projects will however only be explored once DISTENDER has a clear idea of its key exploitable results. The suggestion will be closely discussed with the WP11 lead and the involved partners from the sister projects.

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Conclusions

The deliverable describes the relevance of networks engagement as a measure to facilitate the sustainability of the results produced throughout DISTENDER, being the identification of collaboration potential and knowledge exchange, as well as outreach and enabling a further utilization of project results. It outlines how and with what activities the awareness, acceptance, and uptake of such can be strengthened among key networks and EU-funded projects in the field of climate change mitigation and adaptation.

For this, relevant networks and thematically relevant EU-funded projects from the same call as DISTENDER, cluster 3 addressing disaster resilient societies, and ongoing H2020 projects have been inventoried. Based on the partners rating of their interest and importance/ influence, they have been assigned suitable engagement levels (keep into account, keep informed, meet their needs, and manage closely). Networks and projects classified to be closely managed have been analysed with respect to the ten sectoral foci for which DISTENDER aims to provide solutions to adapt to and mitigate climate change. All sectors offer thematic intersections while quality of life, biodiversity, and finance are foremostly addressed. The analysis offers a starting point for thematically oriented networking activities.

The inventory builds on information stemming from the GA and a survey which has been conducted among project partners to capture their expectations, as well as their envisioned contributions on this task. A networks engagement strategy has been formulated by taking into account the different engagement levels, resulting in pull communication, push communication, consultation, participation, and partnership. Each engagement approach is explained with suitable examples for DISTENDER and linked to the proposed engagement activities. Finally, a tentative timeline has been presented which includes networking activities until M11 and provides an outlook onto the upcoming years. By also describing the connection to overall DISTENDER monitoring in WP10, as well as WP2 and WP9, the deliverable is tied into related project activities.

Appendix

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Annex 1: EU projects funded within the same call as DISTENDER with respect to DISTENDER sectors

Other projects in Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01					
Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Starting date	End Date
FOCI	Non-CO2 Forcers and their Climate, Weather, Air Quality and Health Impacts	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-01 - Improved understanding of greenhouse gas fluxes and radiative forcers, including carbon dioxide removal technologies	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026
GreenFeedBack	GREENHOUSE GAS FLUXES AND EARTH SYSTEM FEEDBACKS	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-01 - Improved understanding of greenhouse gas fluxes and radiative forcers, including carbon dioxide removal technologies	RIA	01.07.2022	30.07.2026
RESCUE	Response of the Earth System to overshoot, Climate neUtrality and negative Emissions	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-01 - Improved understanding of greenhouse gas fluxes and radiative forcers, including carbon dioxide removal technologies	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026
CircoMod	Circular Economy Modelling for Climate Change Mitigation	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-02 - Modelling the role of the circular economy for climate change mitigation	RIA	01.06.2022	31.05.2026
CircEUlar	Developing circular pathways for a EU low-carbon transition	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-02 - Modelling the role of the circular economy for climate change mitigation	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026
CO2NSTRUCT	Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-02 - Modelling the role of the circular economy for climate change mitigation	RIA	01.06.2022	31.05.2026
MAIA	Maximising impact and accessibility of european climate research	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 - Maximising the impact and synergy of European climate change research and innovation	CSA	01.09.2022	31.08.2025
MAGICA	MAXimising the synergy of European research Governance and Innovation for Climate Action	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 - Maximising the impact and synergy of European climate change research and innovation	CSA	01.06.2022	31.05.2026
ELEVATE no website yet	ENABLING AND LEVERAGING CLIMATE ACTION TOWARDS NET-ZERO EMISSIONS	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-04 - Enhanced integrated assessment in pursuit of global climate goals	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026
IAM COMPACT	Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-04 - Enhanced integrated assessment in pursuit of global climate goals	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2025
KNOWING	Framework for defining climate mitigation pathways based on understanding and integrated assessment of climate impacts, adaptation strategies and societal transformation	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-05 - Better understanding of the interactions between climate change impacts and risks, mitigation and adaptation options	RIA	01.06.2022	31.05.2026
Climateurope2	Supporting and standardizing climate services in Europe and beyond	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-06 - Supporting and standardising climate services	CSA	01.09.2022	28.02.2027
NEVERMORE	New Enabling Visions and tools for End-useRs and stakeholders thanks to a common MOdeling fRamework towards a climatE neutral and resilient society	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-05 - Better understanding of the interactions between climate change impacts and risks, mitigation and adaptation options	RIA	01.06.2022	31.05.2026

Other projects in Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01					
Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Starting date	End Date
CAPABLE	ClimAte Policy AcceptaBiLity Economic framework	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-07 - Improved economic methods for decision-making on climate and environmental policies	RIA	01.01.2023	31.12.2025
DECIPHER no website yet	Decision-making framework and processes for holistic evaluation of environmental and climate policies	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-07 - Improved economic methods for decision-making on climate and environmental policies	RIA	01.10.2022	30.09.2025
PATTERN	Providing operational economic appraisal methods and practices for informed decision-making in climate and environmental policies	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-07 - Improved economic methods for decision-making on climate and environmental policies	RIA	01.06.2022	31.05.2025
ALFAwetlands	Wetland restoration for the future	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-08 - Restoration of natural wetlands, peatlands and floodplains as a strategy for fast mitigation benefits; pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.06.2022	30.11.2026
RESTORE4Cs no website yet	Modelling RESTORation of wEtlands for Carbon pathways, Climate Change mitigation and adaptation, ecosystem services, and biodiversity, Co-benefits	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-08 - Restoration of natural wetlands, peatlands and floodplains as a strategy for fast mitigation benefits; pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.01.2023	31.12.2025
REWET	REstoration of WETlands to minimise emissions and maximise carbon uptake – a strategy for long term climate mitigation	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-08 - Restoration of natural wetlands, peatlands and floodplains as a strategy for fast mitigation benefits; pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.10.2022	30.09.2026
WET HORIZONS	Upgrading knowledge and solutions to fast-track wetland restoration across Europe	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-08 - Restoration of natural wetlands, peatlands and floodplains as a strategy for fast mitigation benefits; pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026
ForestNavigator	Navigating European Forests and forest bioeconomy sustainably to EU climate neutrality	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-09 - The contribution of forest management to climate action: pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.09.2022	30.09.2026
ForestPaths	Co-designing Holistic Forest-based Policy Pathways for Climate Change Mitigation	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-09 - The contribution of forest management to climate action: pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.09.2022	28.02.2027
PathFinder no website yet	Towards an Integrated Consistent European LULUCF Monitoring and Policy Pathway Assessment Framework.	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-09 - The contribution of forest management to climate action: pathways, trade-offs and co-benefits	RIA	01.09.2022	31.08.2026

Annex 2: EU projects funded within Cluster 3 on Disaster Resilient Societies with respect to DISTENDER sectors

Projects in Cluster 3: Disaster Resilient Societies					
Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Starting date	End Date
C2IMPRESS	CO-CREATIVE IMPROVED UNDERSTANDING AND AWARENESS OF MULTI-HAZARD RISKS FOR DISASTER RESILIENT SOCIETY	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-01 - Improved understanding of risk exposure and its public awareness in areas exposed to multi-hazards	RIA	01.10.2022	30.09.2025
DIRECTED	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing interoperable Data, models, communication and governance	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02 - Integrated Disaster Risk Reduction for extreme climate events: from early warning systems to long term adaptation and resilience building	IA	01.10.2022	30.09.2026
The HuT	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02 - Integrated Disaster Risk Reduction for extreme climate events: from early warning systems to long term adaptation and resilience building	IA	01.10.2022	30.09.2026
MEDiate	Multi-hazard and risk informed system for Enhanced local and regional Disaster risk management	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-03 - Enhanced assessment of disaster risks, adaptive capabilities and scenario building based on available historical data and projections	RIA	01.10.2022	30.09.2025

Projects in Cluster 3: Disaster Resilient Societies

Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Starting date	End Date
PARATUS	Promoting disaster preparedness and resilience by co-developing stakeholder support tools for managing the systemic risk of compounding disasters	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-03 - Enhanced assessment of disaster risks, adaptive capabilities and scenario building based on available historical data and projections	RIA	01.10.2022	30.09.2026
PEERS	PracticE Ecosystem for standaRdS	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-04 - Developing a prioritisation mechanism for research programming in standardisation related to natural hazards and/or CBRN-E sectors	CSA	01.11.2022	31.10.2025
MOBILISE	A novel and green mobile One Health laboratory for (re-)emerging infectious disease outbreaks	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-05 - Fast deployed mobile laboratories to enhance situational awareness for pandemics and emerging infectious diseases	IA	01.10.2022	30.09.2025
ONELAB	Orchestrating next-generation mobile modular laboratories for pandemic monitoring preparedness	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-05 - Fast deployed mobile laboratories to enhance situational awareness for pandemics and emerging infectious diseases	IA	01.10.2022	30.09.2025

Annex 3: Ongoing H2020 projects with respect to DISTENDER sectors

Running projects in Horizon2020					
Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Start date	End date
EMB3Rs	User-driven Energy-Matching & Business prospection tool for industrial Excess heat/cold Reduction, Recovery and Redistribution	LC-SC3-EE-6-2018-2019-2020 - Business case for industrial waste heat/cold recovery	IA	02.09.2019	01.06.2023
DRYvER	Securing biodiversity, functional integrity and ecosystem services in DRYing rivER networks	LC-CLA-06-2019 - Inter-relations between climate change, biodiversity and ecosystem services	RIA	01.09.2020	31.08.2024
BiodivScen	Promoting and implementing joint programming at the international level to reinforce research on the development of scenarios of biodiversity and ecosystem services	SC5-32-2017 - Biodiversity scenarios	ERA-NET-Cofund - ERA-NET Cofund	01.10.2017	30.06.2023
MIND STEP	Modelling INdividual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture	RUR-04-2018-2019 - Analytical tools and models to support policies related to agriculture and food	RIA	01.09.2019	31.12.2023
BiodivClim	Promoting and implementing joint programming to reinforce transnational research at the crossroad between biodiversity and climate change	LC-CLA-09-2019 - ERA-NET Cofund action on biodiversity and climate change: Impacts, feedbacks, and nature-based solutions for climate change adaptation and mitigation	ERA-NET-Cofund - ERA-NET Cofund	01.09.2019	31.08.2024
RECEIPT	REmote Climate Effects and their Impact on European sustainability, Policy and Trade	LC-CLA-03-2018 - Climate change impacts in Europe	RIA	01.09.2019	31.08.2023
CASCADES	CAScading Climate risks: towards ADaptive and resilient European Societies	LC-CLA-03-2018 - Climate change impacts in Europe	RIA	01.09.2019	31.08.2023
NAVIGATE	Next generation of AdVanced InteGrated Assessment modelling to support climaTE policy making	LC-CLA-01-2018 - Supporting the development of climate policies to deliver on the Paris Agreement, through Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs)	RIA	01.09.2019	31.08.2023
ENGAGE	Exploring National and Global Actions to reduce Greenhouse gas Emissions	LC-CLA-01-2018 - Supporting the development of climate policies to deliver on the Paris Agreement, through Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs)	RIA	01.09.2019	31.08.2023

Running projects in Horizon2020					
Acronym	Full Title	Call Topic	Funding Scheme	Start date	End date
CityxChange	Positive City ExChange	<u>LC-SC3-SCC-1-2018-2019-2020 - Smart Cities and Communities</u>	IA	01.11.2018	31.10.2023
POCITYE	A POsitive Energy CITY Transformation Framework	<u>LC-SC3-SCC-1-2018-2019-2020 - Smart Cities and Communities</u>	IA	01.10.2019	30.09.2024
eLTER PLUS	European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS	<u>INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 - Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities</u>	RIA	01.02.2020	31.01.2025
FOOD TRAILS	Building pathways towards FOOD 2030-led urban food policies	<u>CE-FNR-07-2020 - FOOD 2030 - Empowering cities as agents of food system transformation</u>	IA	16.10.2020	15.10.2024
NEGEM	Quantifying and Deploying Responsible Negative Emissions in Climate Resilient Pathways	<u>LC-CLA-02-2019 - Negative emissions and land-use based mitigation assessment</u>	RIA	01.06.2020	31.05.2024
RESPONSE	integRatEd Solutions for POsitive eNergy and reSilient CitiEs	<u>LC-SC3-SCC-1-2018-2019-2020 - Smart Cities and Communities</u>	IA	01.10.2020	30.09.2025

